

Influence of NPK levels and split N application on grain filling and yield of fine rice

M. Asif, F.M. Chaudhary, and M. Saeed, Agronomy Department, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad 38040, Pakistan

The major causes of low rice yield and poor grain filling of rice in Pakistan are the unbalanced use of NPK and higher N losses due to bulk N application at transplanting. We designed a field experiment to test the hypothesis that a balanced supply of NPK and split application of N would improve both grain filling and yield of Basmati 385. The soil in the experimental plots was a clay loam with 0.73% organic matter, 0.046% total N, 4.9 ppm P, and pH 7.7.

Treatments consisted of three nutrient levels (60-0-0 [F₁], 130-67-67 [F₂], and 180-90-90 kg NPK ha⁻¹ [F₃]) and three N application times (all at transplanting [N₁], 1/2 at transplanting + 1/2 at early tillering [N₂], and 1/3 each at transplanting + early tillering + panicle initiation [N₃]). The ex-

periment was laid out in a split-plot design with nutrient level as the main plot and time of N application as the subplot with four replications. NPK was supplied as urea, single superphosphate, and sulfate of potash. P and K were applied basally.

Nutrient level F₂ significantly reduced the occurrence of sterile spikelets, opaque spikelets, and chalky kernels (see table), while it significantly increased the proportion of normal kernels, probably because of sufficient availability of plant nutrients at the early, middle, and later stages of kernel development. Moreover, less lodging occurred in this treatment compared with higher NPK levels in the F₃ treatment (data not shown). Lodging may have interrupted the continuous translo-

cation of carbohydrates to the panicle. The F₂ treatment also improved grain yield and yield components such as panicles m⁻² and 1000-grain weight.

Three splits of N fertilizer (N₃) resulted in less abortive spikelets and chalky kernels and a higher proportion of normal kernels compared with bulk application of N (N₁) at transplanting. Yield and yield components such as panicles m⁻², spikelets panicle⁻¹, percentage of filled spikelets, and 1000-grain weight increased significantly in response to split N application. The three splits sustained the supply of N throughout the vegetative and reproductive development of the plant, particularly during grain filling and ripening. However, a reverse trend was observed for

Effects of different NPK levels and split application of N on grain filling, yield, and yield components of Basmati 385, 1995-96^a kharif season.^b

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Spikelets m ⁻² (no. x 1000)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Filled spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (%)	Grain filling (%)	Sterile spikelets ^c (%)	Abortive spikelets (%)	Opaque spikelets ^d (%)	Chalky kernels ^e (%)	Normal kernels ^f (%)	1000-grain wt(g)
<i>NPK level (kg ha⁻¹)</i>												
F ₁ = 60-0-0	3.6 b	230 b	49.75 b	216	170 c	78.8	16.1 a	5.4 b	9.3 a	42.7 a	69.5 b	15.4 b
F ₂ = 130-67-67	4.4 a	300 a	68.37 a	228	185 b	81.3	12.6 b	6.1 ab	7.8 b	27.4 c	73.5 a	15.8 a
F ₃ = 180-90-90	4.2 a	298 a	68.51 a	230	121 a	78.9	13.8 b	7.7 a	9.1 a	31.7 b	69.8 b	15.6 a
LSD	0.22	14.5	2.17	ns	11.1	ns	1.29	1.71	0.87	2.79	2.24	0.23
<i>N application technique</i>												
N ₁ = all N at transplanting												
N ₂ = 1/2 N at transplanting + 1/2 N at early tillering	3.8 b	268 b	56.87 c	213 b	164 c	77.3 b	16.3 a	6.9 a	8.1 b	35.8 a	69.2 b	15.3 b
N ₃ = 1/3 N at transplanting + 1/3 N at early tillering + 1/3 N at panicle initiation	4.1 a	273 ab	60.85 b	223 b	178 b	79.7 ab	12.6 b	7.3 a	8.5 b	33.2 b	71.2 ab	15.6 a
LSD	0.20	10.6	3.01	10.64	9.71	3.17	1.53	0.84	0.69	1.97	2.06	0.21
C = A x B0	ns ^g	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aResults were averaged for 1995 and 1996. ^bWithin a column and treatment group, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of probability. ^cUnfertilized or unfilled empty spikelets. ^dSpikelets that get fertilized but do not attain full size as they stop growing during the early stage of grain filling. ^eKernels with the whole, one-half, or more of the surface white like the color of chalk due to abnormal accumulation of photosynthates during grain filling. ^fKernels that attain full size, turn translucent, and show normal starch compaction. ^gns = not significant.

opaque spikelets. The longer panicles with more spikelets resulted in severe competition for photosynthates, which led to a higher proportion of opaque spikelets.

The application of 130-67-67 kg NPK ha⁻¹ and N in three splits to Basmati 385 resulted in higher grain yield with a higher

percentage of grain filling and normal kernels due to a considerable reduction in sterility, abortiveness, and chalkiness.

The adaptability of *Azolla mexicana* in the Ege region of Turkey

M.N. Gevrek, Field Crops Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Ege University, Izmir 35100, Turkey

The Ege region on the west coast of Turkey has a distinct climate—temperature ranges from 15 to 35 °C from the beginning of April to the first week of September, rainfall averages 500-600 mm, and relative humidity is 57%. Summer is warm and dry while winter is mild and rainy.

Of four different *Azolla* strains obtained (*A. microphylla* 4030, IRRI; *A. microphylla* 4089, China; *A. filiculoides* 1001; and *A. mexicana* 2026), *A. mexicana* 2026 was found adaptable to Izmir ecological conditions. In 1995, a field experiment was conducted to determine the suitable inoculation time for *A. mexicana*. *A. mexicana* was first grown at Izmir and then transferred to the rice experimental fields at Menemen (sandy loam soil, 0.9% organic matter, and pH 6.9). Rice variety TOAG-92 was used in the experiment.

Four different inoculation times were tested one after the other on the same plots. A randomized complete block design with three replications was used in the rice fields. For each application time, 300 g of fresh *Azolla* was inoculated per square meter and allowed to grow for 14 d. When the surface was covered with *Azolla* (7-10 d after inoculation), 0.2 g P₂O₅ m⁻² was applied. *Azolla* biomass was collected and fresh weight, dry weight, and total N were measured (Table 1). The first inoculation of *Azolla* was done when the rice plants were at the 3-leaf stage.

The inoculated amount of fresh weight (300 g m⁻²) increased to 1122 g m⁻² after 14 d (274%). Statistical analysis showed that the first inoculation dates resulted in comparatively better yield perfor-

mance than any other inoculation dates based on Duncan's multiple range test. The best time for *Azolla* inoculation was the first week of July (1200 g m⁻²) (see table). However, inoculating *Azolla* at the end of August also gave a reasonable amount of *Azolla*. N was 0.33% in fresh *Azolla*, and mean N gain was 2.7 g m⁻².

The effect of *A. mexicana* on soil N mineralization was also investigated in 1996. Incubation studies using fresh and dried *Azolla* were conducted in the laboratory. *Azolla* was placed on top of half of a sample of air-dried sandy loam soil in a test tube (2-cm-diam); the other half of the

soil was placed on top of the *Azolla* in another test tube. Both were flooded to a 5-cm depth with distilled water to keep the *Azolla* from floating. More *Azolla* was added to give about 5 mg N test tube⁻¹. Tubes were then incubated in the dark at 30°C. Results are shown in Table 2. N release was more rapid from dried *Azolla* (56%) than from fresh *Azolla* (38%). The *Azolla* totally decomposed after 2-3 wk and increased the total soil N by 38-56%, contributing to total soil organic matter. Organic matter release was more rapid from dried *Azolla* (40%) than from fresh *Azolla* (31%).

Table 1. Average growth and nitrogen accumulation in the *Azolla*-inoculated field plots, Izmir, Turkey, 1995.

Treatment	Inoculation date	Mean temperature (°C)	Amount harvested (g m ⁻²)	% increase in fresh weight	N increase (g m ⁻²)
1	10 Jul	30.0	1200 a	300	3.0 a
2	24 Jul	30.6	1090 bc	263	2.6 bc
3	7 Aug	27.4	1060 c	253	2.5 c
4	21 Aug	27.4	1140 ab	280	2.8 ab
Av		28.9	1122	274	2.7
SD				60	0.10

Table 2. Increase in total N and organic matter content of soil incubated with *A. mexicana*.

Week	Control soil	% increase			
		Total N		Organic matter	
		Fresh	Dried	Fresh	Dried
1	100	127.5 b	122.9 e	114.0 c	105.5 e
2	100	137.5 a	135.4 c	130.5 a	138.8 a
3	100	133.3 a	155.5 a	128.8 a	140.0 a
4	100	133.3 a	144.4 b	122.1 b	134.2 a
5	100	126.6 b	133.3 cd	114.2 c	125.5 c
6	100	122.2 c	131.1 d	108.6 d	120.3 d